

ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS ON EMOTIONAL

ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS ON EMOTIONAL WELL-BEING

ABSTRACT:

The environment and the set of environmental factors that surround us can have a great influence on the perceived sense of well-being. However, there are few studies that jointly analyze the influence of a selection of factors for the conformation of environments that favor well-being, especially in young adults (under 40 years of age) in active employment. It is in this context that the present research arises, whose objective is to determine the influence that a set of eight selected factors has on the emotional well-being of a selection of people in their work environment.

For this purpose, a set of 15 experiments are carried out, using collections of images to assess the emotional interpretation of each individual under the influence of the conditions of their environment, processing and analyzing the data obtained by means of Soft Computing techniques.

The analysis carried out indicates that lighting and room temperature are the most influential factors in emotional well-being. On the second level, the availability of food/drink is relatively decisive. This knowledge can be used for the design of work environments capable of favouring emotional well-being and consequently work productivity.

Keywords: Emotional interpretation, environmental factors, pattern recognition, Soft Computing, clustering.

RESUMEN:

El entorno y el conjunto de factores ambientales que nos rodean pueden suponer una gran influencia en la sensación de bienestar percibida. Sin embargo, son escasos los trabajos que analizan conjuntamente la influencia de una selección de factores para la conformación de entornos favorecedores del bienestar, especialmente en adultos jóvenes (menores de 40 años) en situación laboral activa. En este contexto surge la presente investigación, cuyo objetivo es de determinar la influencia que un conjunto de ocho factores seleccionados tiene sobre el bienestar emocional de una selección de personas en su entorno laboral.

Para ello, se realiza un conjunto de 15 experimentos, utilizando colecciones de imágenes para valorar la interpretación emocional de cada individuo bajo la influencia de las condiciones de su entorno, tratando y analizando los datos obtenidos mediante técnicas de Soft Computing.

El análisis realizado indica que la iluminación y temperatura ambiente son los factores más influyentes en el bienestar emocional. En su segundo nivel, la posibilidad de contar con comida/bebida, resulta relativamente determinante. Este conocimiento puede ser utilizado para el diseño de entornos de trabajo capaces de favorecer el bienestar emocional y consecuentemente la productividad laboral

Palabras clave: Interpretación emocional, factores ambientales, reconocimiento de patrones, Soft Computing, clustering

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1.- INTRODUCTION

In any living environment, the set of environmental factors surrounding a person is capable of influencing their emotional well-being [1]-[3]. In some cases, the existence of these factors may be known a priori, and in others the factors turn out to be totally unpredictable in nature, making it even more difficult to foresee or mitigate the effects that their presence may cause. For this reason, assessing the influence that certain environmental parameters may have on the mood or mental state of a person is an area of great interest [4]-[9].

For this reason, literature reviews [10] [3] report the existence of different researches focused on assessing the influence of certain factors on mood or productivity in different contexts.

Thus, research focused on academia, such as [11] and [4], try to analyze the influence of classroom color on the well-being of their students, also considering the effect of lighting on perceived color [12].

Analogously, but focused on adulthood, are relevant works that try to analyze the influence of music, through sessions based on music therapy [13]-[15], environmental noise [5][8] [16]-[19], climate [20]-[23], social environment [5] [7][19] [19][24] [25], proximity to green spaces [18] [26], and environmental stress [27]. Additionally, works such as [28] and [29] in which the use of sensors to monitor facial and gestural expression, physiological parameters, activity and behavior of advanced people, with the aim of recognizing their emotions, analyzing how music, color and light are able to stimulate their emotions towards a positive and pleasant mood, are significant.

Finally, in the workplace, several studies have investigated the influence of artificial ambient light [30]-[32], natural lighting [33], temperature [34], or even light and temperature together [2] [35].

However, most of the current studies focus on verifying whether a set of factors is determinant or not in the performance of a particular task, leaving in the background the degree of influence depending on other circumstances, as well as the assessment of other factors, so far less analyzed (such as the presence of food/drink, the color of the walls or the level of interruptions), which could also be relevant.

In this context, the present work arises, with the aim of determining which factors are more relevant, trying to determine their degree of influence. For this purpose, a set of experiments is carried out with a selection of people of similar characteristics (age, education, etc.), simulating different situations and external factors, during the development of a simple task: to observe a set of images, of different categories, and to evaluate the feeling that each of them produces in them according to a determined scale of values. However, obtaining the degree of influence of each of the factors, when they are combined to form different situations, is a complex process. For this reason, different Soft Computing techniques are used, a subset of tools belonging to the field of Artificial Intelligence with the ability to address problems that handle incomplete information or uncertainty, such as similarity matrices [36], dendrograms [37] and CART-type decision trees [38] [39], in order to determine which factors are more influential in the emotional interpretation of different sets of visual stimuli.

2.- MATERIAL AND METHOD

In order to determine which external factors are more influential during the execution of a task, a model based on data analytics and the use of Soft Computing techniques is proposed to identify those that have a greater impact. Knowing these factors is especially important to try to achieve environments that allow greater comfort, either in order to achieve greater well-being or to perform tasks with greater productivity.

Figure 1 shows the general framework of the proposed method.

Fig. 1. General framework

Participants

To carry out the experiments, five volunteers (100% men) with epidemiological characteristics without significant differences, in the same age range between 29 and 34 years (M: 32.3; SD: 3.1), with similar education (engineering) and profession (software design) were selected. All of them performed their work in an office environment with intensive use of data visualization screens (DSPs).

To find out the sample power, the required effect size (degree to which the null hypothesis is false, [40]) is calculated using G*Power (version 3.1.9.6). In a repeated measures experiment, with 5 participants and 15 different experimental conditions, with an error $\alpha=0.05$, a power ($1-\beta$ err prob) = 0.95, a non-centrality parameter $\lambda=33.18$, non-sphericity correction $\epsilon=1$, with 14 and 56 degrees of freedom, a critical value of $F = 1.87$ and an effect size $f = 0.47$ have been obtained.

The mission of the participants during the experiments, in which different environmental conditions are simulated (Table 1), is to evaluate the impression they get from looking at different sets of photographs according to specific scales.

Instruments

The set of 1200 images provided by the International Affective Picture System (IAPS) [41] developed and distributed by the NIMH Center for Emotion and Attention (CSEA) at the University of Florida with the aim of providing standardized materials for researchers specializing in the study of emotion and attention is used to conduct the experiments. This collection of images contains photographs of different categories: happy people, landscapes, animals, violent scenes, etc., with the aim of eliciting different emotions.

Starting from a set of 1200 images, the collection is divided into 15 sets of 80 images each, in order to perform 15 experiments. To configure the 15 environments associated with each of the experiments, 8 easily configurable factors are selected. Each of these is described below.

- Time: represents the time of day when the experiment is carried out.
- Lighting: artificial lighting is used, with different intensities.
- Room temperature: the temperature is set by means of hot/cold air conditioners.
- Ambient music: different types of ambient music can be set using a music player.
- Interruptions: number of planned interruptions.
- Color of the walls: relative to the room where the experiment is performed.
- Food/drink: presence or absence of food and/or drink.
- Weather: outdoor weather during the experiment.

Table 1 shows the factors considered and their possible values.

External factor	Possible values		
F1: Timetable	1: Morning (9:00h)	2: Noon (15:00h)	3: Afternoon (19:00)
F2: Lighting	1: High	2: Medium	3: Low
F3: Temperature	1: Heat (28°C)	2: Comfort (21°C)	3: Cold (16°C)
F4: Ambient music	1: No music	2: Classical music	3: Pop music
F5: Interruptions	1: No	2: Moderate	3: Numerous
F6: Wall color	1: White	2: Blue	3: Combination
F7: Food/drink	1: Nothing	2: Water	3: Food and water
F8: Time	1: Sunny	2: Cloudy	3: Rainy

Table 1. External factors and possible values

Taking into account the above factors, it would be possible to make up 38=6521 different environments. Considering that it would be unfeasible to carry out such a large number of experiments, the most common combinations of factors are selected, giving rise to 15 configurations, and therefore 15 experiments, as shown in Table 2.

Experiment	Value for each external factor							
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
Exp0	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1
Exp1	1	2	3	1	1	1	3	1
Exp2	1	3	3	2	2	3	3	2
Exp3	1	1	2	2	1	1	2	1
Exp4	1	3	1	1	2	1	1	3
Exp5	2	3	1	3	3	2	1	1
Exp6	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	1
Exp7	2	1	2	3	1	3	2	2
Exp8	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	1
Exp9	2	2	3	2	2	1	3	1
Exp10	3	3	1	1	1	3	1	3
Exp11	3	2	3	1	1	1	3	1
Exp12	3	2	3	3	3	1	3	1
Exp13	3	1	2	1	1	3	2	2
Exp14	3	3	1	3	2	1	1	1

Table 2. Experiments carried out

Procedures

To carry out the experiments, a set of participants with similar characteristics in terms of age, education and profession are selected. Their mission is to observe a collection of photographs specifically designed for the evaluation of perceived emotions, and to rate from 1 to 10 the following pairs of feelings produced by each one:

- Happiness vs. Sadness (valencia).
- Calmness vs. Excitement (excitement).
- Under Control vs. Out of Control (dominance).

During each experiment participants view a set of 80 images specifically selected from the total of 1200 provided by the International Affective Picture System (IAPS)[41]. Since the original collection contains images belonging to different categories, 4 images are selected from each of the following 20 categories, trying to maintain the mean values of arousal, valence and dominance: clothed and naked people, houses, art objects, domestic objects, housing projects, funerals, pollution, dirty toilets, cityscapes, seascapes,

sporting events, wars, disasters, medical treatments, sick patients, dangerous animals, insects, families, waterfalls and children playing.

Before starting the experiments, the conditions under which the experiments would be carried out are explained to each participant. They are also offered the possibility of not evaluating images that could offend their sensibilities. Additionally, they must accept and sign an informed consent form, authorizing the dissemination of the results of the experiment, while maintaining anonymity.

The execution of the experiments is carried out in different rooms, in which the existence of different factors is controlled or simulated, namely: time, lighting, room temperature, background music, level of interruptions, colour of the walls, presence or absence of food/drink, and time. Considering different combinations of these factors, a set of experiments are carried out with the aim of simulating different environments in order to determine the most influential factors in the results obtained.

The set of answers given by each participant in each experiment is considered as a source of data for the following phases of data analysis and knowledge extraction. Thus, by aggregating and averaging the ratings given by the participants for each pair of emotions when observing each image, it is possible to obtain the mean values for each emotion in each experiment.

Data analysis

During this phase, the aim is to discover which external factors are the most influential for the emotional interpretation of visual stimuli. Since the objective is to calculate the degree of influence of each of the factors, something that is complex when these factors are combined with different parameterizations to form different situations, we resort to the use of Soft Computing techniques, a branch of Artificial Intelligence that encompasses various techniques capable of addressing problems that handle incomplete information, with uncertainty and/or inaccurate. Specifically, we propose the execution of a process based on 2 phases, where different Soft Computing techniques are combined:

1. Generation of a dendrogram by applying a hierarchical clustering algorithm [37] supported by the use of the machine learning platform Weka [42] and the specific development in Python programming language and the Spyder IDE development environment. Dendrograms are powerful tools for the generation of clusters, or groups of elements, with similar characteristics. To do this, we start from the average rating data obtained for each pair of feelings in each experiment, applying a process on them, obtained a classification, forced to three groups, in relation to the outcome of the experiments. Those in which a low value (less than 5) is obtained for the 3 pairs of emotions considered are classified as experiments in which the configured environment is "negative", those in which a high average value is obtained (greater than 7.5) are considered as "positive", and the rest as "neutral".
2. Application of CART-type decision trees as originally proposed by Brian [43] and Quilan [44] or evolved by Alsolami [38] and Kretowski [39], developed specifically in this research using the Python programming language and the Spyder IDE development environment. Decision trees are tools with the ability to detect rules and relationships, capable, in this context, of determining the relationships of influence between the external factors considered in each experiment and the result obtained. To do this, we start from the classification obtained for each experiment and the values of the factors established in each of them. Thus, after the application of the decision tree, it is possible to obtain a selection and ordering of the factors that are most influential in the conformation of environments more favourable to well-being.

Once we have discovered which factors are most influential in the emotional interpretation of images, it is possible to make the right decisions to establish work or living environments that offer greater well-being.

3.- RESULTS

After conducting the experiments, the mean of the ratings made by the participants was calculated, thus obtaining an overall rating for each experiment with respect to the 3 groups of emotions considered. Table 3 shows the mean values obtained for each pair of feelings rated in each experiment.

Experiment	Valencia	Excitement	Dominance
Exp0	6,62	7,23	8,03
Exp1	6,21	5,42	6,05
Exp2	5,91	5,35	4,39
Exp3	8,11	6,86	6,55
Exp4	4,83	4,26	4,60
Exp5	5,15	4,35	4,12
Exp6	6,47	7,41	4,72
Exp7	7,36	7,35	7,20
Exp8	7,59	7,44	6,78
Exp9	6,14	6,15	4,58
Exp10	4,42	5,29	4,40
Exp11	4,62	5,90	6,15
Exp12	6,31	5,20	5,65
Exp13	6,55	7,58	6,86

Exp14	3,81	4,91	4,31
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Table 3. Results of the experiments

Subsequently, the knowledge extraction phase was carried out. By generating a dendrogram with the data obtained, a rating of the result of the experiments is obtained, considering that the best environments are those that promote better feelings of happiness, control and calm. Figure 2 shows the 3 groups of experiments obtained.

Fig. 2. Classification of experiments by dendrogram.

In Figure 2, the abscissa axis represents the identifier of each experiment, and the ordinate axis indicates the similarity between the results obtained by the experiments according to the ratings obtained for each pair of emotions. Thus, the lower the horizontal line joining each pair or each group of experiments, the more similar they are to each other.

The dendrogram reveals three considerably homogeneous groups. The first group, categorized as experiments with a "negative" outcome, is the one composed of the experiments with the lowest scores for the three dimensions: Exp2, Exp4, Exp5, Exp10, Exp14. The second group, which we call "neutral", comprises the experiments with average scores: Exp1, Exp6, Exp9, Exp11, Exp12. Finally, the third group, which we call "positive", included the experiments that scored the highest in positive emotions: Exp0, Exp3, Exp7, Exp8, Exp13.

Table 4 shows the mean values obtained for each sentiment pair according to the clustering achieved.

Experiment	Valencia	Excitement	Dominance
Experiments with "positive" results	7,20	7,28	7,09
Experiments with a "neutral" result	5,86	5,93	5,35
Experiments with "negative" results	4,72	4,79	4,36

Table 4. Average evaluation of experiments

Once the different groups have been obtained, the objective is to determine which factors are the most influential. To do this, an analysis based on decision trees is carried out. The process for its generation starts from the classification obtained for each of the experiments and the values established for each of the determining factors, detecting which factors and values lead to one or another classification. Figure 3 shows a decision tree generated from the classification obtained by the dendrogram. For its elaboration, an extension of the CART decision tree algorithm [38] [39] has been applied, establishing a statistical pruning to avoid overlearning.

Figure 3. Influence of the factors using decision trees

With this representation it is observed that the factors F2 (illumination), F3 (temperature) and F7 (food/drink) are the most influential. The rest of the factors are discriminated, as it is considered that they do not affect the evaluation of the result of the experiments. However, to quantify the level of influence of each factor, Figure 4 shows the percentage of significance obtained by running the algorithm using the BigML machine learning platform [45].

Figure 4. Importance of each factor

According to the data obtained, factors F2 and F3 would have a high classifying power, while factor F7 would have a lower level of significant influence.

Once the most influential factors and their optimal values are known, a new environment is prepared in which the most appropriate conditions are established (high lighting, comfortable temperature and presence of food and drink), thus creating an optimized environment to promote emotional well-being. After this, a last and new experiment is carried out, following the same steps detailed above, obtaining the results shown in Table 5.

Experiment	Valencia	Excitement	Dominance
Experiment in an optimized environment	7,78	7,92	7,63

Table 5. Average values in optimized environment

The values obtained in this last experiment with an optimal configuration in the most influential factors are clearly better than those obtained in the 15 experiments carried out initially, even considering the classification by groups carried out, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Comparison of results obtained

The comparison between the results calculated in all the experiments carried out and the values obtained in the new environment under optimized conditions obtains significantly better scores in the three pairs of emotions analyzed ("valence", "arousal" and "dominance").

4.- DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Determining the degree of influence of a selection of factors on the emotional well-being of young adults in active employment is a challenge of interest and object of study in different disciplines. In this work, a set of controlled experiments have been modelled and carried out, the results of which have been processed and analysed using different techniques belonging to the field of Soft Computing, demonstrating their usefulness in quantifying the influence of each of the selected factors. The results obtained highlight the importance of 3 of them, discarding the rest. In addition, by reviewing the results obtained, it is possible to know the most appropriate settings to achieve greater emotional well-being.

Factor	Relevance	Optimum value
F2: Lighting	43,25%	1: High
F3: Ambient temperature	34,40%	2: Comfort (21°C)
F7: Presence of food and/or drink	6,40%	3: Food and water

Table 6. Relevance and optimal values of the most influential factors

According to the data obtained, in the first place, lighting is a clearly influential factor (43.25%), something shared by other research [30][32], confirming that the presence of a powerful light source that provides clarity is directly related to a greater feeling of comfort and well-being. It is important to point out that in the experiments carried out, artificial light sources were used, without discriminating by tonality. This fact prevents us from drawing conclusions about the influence of tonality and natural light, effects analyzed by [31][33].

Secondly, the ambient temperature is also shown as a factor of significant influence (34.40%), indicating that a comfortable value (21°C) can favour the feeling of well-being. Previous relevant studies [2][35] confirm this fact.

Finally, the existence of food/drink shows a relative capacity of influence (6.47%). However, no studies have been found that, in comparable situations, confirm or refute this result.

The rest of the factors analysed were discarded, as they were assessed as having little influence, always taking into account the limitation of the work the set of experiments carried out and the limitation of the sample. In the group of factors with non-significant relevance, it is interesting to highlight the factor related to the color of the walls, due to the existence of works specifically focused on the analysis of its influence [11][46], in which an influence of its tones on perceived well-being is detected. Although this fact may seem contradictory, it is important to consider that the colors used in the experiments carried out (blue, white and mixed) were in all cases of low or very low intensity. This fact could justify and align the results obtained with those of the aforementioned studies.

The knowledge obtained about the level of influence of the analyzed factors can be used to try to shape better coexistence environments, capable of favoring the feeling of well-being, as was proved by repeating the experiment under the considered optimal conditions, showing an improvement of 31.27%, 32% and 36.25%, respectively, in the three feelings analyzed (valence, arousal and dominance) compared to the average values of the 15 experiments carried out. This information is key for the design of working

environments in offices, especially for young adults with regular use of PVD, considering that the establishment of a powerful light source, a temperature around 21°C, and the possibility of having a supply of food and drink, can improve the feeling of well-being by more than 30%.

5.- LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In addition to the aforementioned limitation derived from the size of the sample, it is important to point out that the fact that participants of different age groups or types of work were not included, which would have allowed us to obtain specific results by age and profession.

It is also necessary to consider that the total participation of each volunteer amounted to a total of about 180 minutes as the sum of their participation in the different experiments, an interval of relevant duration that could have influenced the capabilities and level of performance of each one, as well as the results obtained. However, having carried out the experiments on different days, without ever exceeding their daily participation by more than 30 minutes, the influence of this factor is considered to have been very limited.

Finally, the fact of having used different groupings of 80 images in the 15 experiments carried out, despite maintaining the same typology and weight by categories, could have affected the results obtained, something that will be considered in future research.

Future work will assess the possibility of using partitioning algorithms such as K-means or Fuzzy C-means [47], or density-based algorithms such as DBSCAN [37] to compare the clustering results obtained in this research using hierarchical algorithms.

In addition, a larger number of participants will be considered with less bias, as well as a larger number of external factors, and a larger number of emotions will also be assessed, with the aim of gaining a broader understanding of the factors that are most influential in determining an optimal work environment.

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